

GUIDELINE FOR OBSERVATIONS IN CIVIL SOCIETY ORGANISATIONS – REINCLUGEN PROJECT

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RESEARCH QUESTIONS AND OBJECTIVES OF THE QUALITATIVE FIELDWORK OF THE REINCLUGEN PROJECT

Before one can use the Guidelines for observations, topic guides for focus group discussions and interview photo-voicing, we briefly set out the objectives and methodological approach of the ReIncluGen project. We highlight recommend that you first have a look at our website: www.reincludgen.be and contact the researchers involved.

OBJECTIVES AND METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH

The qualitative research part of the ReIncluGen project addresses directly the second objective of the project to use a bottom-up and participatory approach to **unpack the different conceptualisations of gender ‘empowerment’ across spheres and contexts by bringing in more nuance and situatedness** in notions of gender ‘empowerment’. In doing so, it aims to move beyond the written diversity and gender equality policies and consider both the heterogeneity and agency of minority groups and women and girls with a migration background.

The main research objective is to understand how migrant women and CSOs conceptualise gender empowerment and is formulated as follows: **“How do CSOs and their members conceptualise gender empowerment?”**. Additionally, we aim to gain more insight in how gender empowerment is experienced, practised, supported and embodied, both by CSO staff and organisational structures, as well as by the participants in their services, activities, and events. Given that we have selected CSOs, both within and outside our consortium, that focus on empowerment, their members could involve both people with and without a migration background. The main focus is on women with a migration background, and thus their views will receive priority within the project, however, we aim to assess all relevant views by also seeing gender as a continuum.

By combining research methods that involve ethnographic observation within CSOs, focus groups discussion (FGD), and photovoice interviews, we aim to identify the spectrum of ideas and concepts, the tensions, and the negotiated meanings of gender empowerment and inclusion, which ultimately result in a re-defined meaning of gender empowerment and possibly re-considered ways of acting upon it.

One of the key contributions of Anthropology is the difference between an **emic** and an **etic** concept. The emic concept is an internally defined concept from inside a community or group. By doing interviews and FGD with CSO participants, who come from different background, we want to unveil their own internal understanding of empowerment and inclusion, and the role of gender). The **etic** concept describes external concepts which come either from theoretical research or from policy development. Our research will combine emic and etic definitions, starting with the emic concept of the research participants and the CSOs, and then moving to comparing them against policy definitions and theoretically constructed definitions of gender empowerment (etic). The word empowerment in itself is difficult to define and difficult to translate. By starting off with the emic approach we will use participatory research methods to elicit its meanings for participants and staff/volunteers.

The empirical research will trace 3 definitions:

- The ways it is understood and named by participants (emic)

- The ways it is used and understood by CSOs (combined)
- Theoretical concept based on policy analysis and scientific literature (etic)

First, we are looking for the emic concept of empowerment – the one that comes from the people we conduct research with. We are interested in whether such a concept exists, if not, what is the closest that people define, and how do they conceptualize it and define it. We do not start from an etic concept in order to avoid external and imposed definitions.

Second, we are looking for the way empowerment is used by CSOs in particular ways that may be different from the definitions of policy documents or the definitions of the research participants who use the CSO services. Moreover, it is used both as a goal and as an indicator of what they do (trying to improve empowerment of women and girls with a migrant background) and how they evaluate the impact of their actions and activities with them. Third, we use the etic concept AFTER analyzing realities and then build it to allow for comparison across the country cases.

Within this broader research question, we developed several sub-questions:

Sub-questions for CSO participants:

- How do women define gender empowerment?
- How do women experience gender empowerment in their everyday lives?
- Which practices make women feel empowered? What are the preconditions to realise these practices?
- How do women define inclusion?
- Which barriers and opportunities do women experience in society?
- Which CSOs practices are perceived to contribute to gender empowerment?
- Is the CSO perceived as being inclusive and welcoming to all (women)?

Sub-questions for CSOs organisers and staff members:

- How do people working at different levels and positions in the CSOs conceptualize gender empowerment?
- How is gender empowerment and inclusion implemented through practices and activities in CSOs?
- What barriers and opportunities do they identify in achieving gender empowerment through their CSO?

For each partner, we envisage additional thematic and context-specific sub-questions that need to be adjusted to the local context, the concrete position of the CSOs in the local policy and funding context, and the specific groups of migrant women participating in the research. In the case of Austria, for example, questions of power dynamics, funding schemes, dependencies on funders and their agenda, burnout of the workforce have been already identified as topics to be further addressed in the FGD with the CSO organisers.

RESEARCH STAGES AND STEPS

OVERVIEW

Three types of research methods will be used to answer the research questions developed in WP2:

- Explorative ethnographic fieldwork in three CSOs
- Focus group discussions with CSO participants and with CSO organizers
- Photo-voicing interviews with female participants of the CSOs

The three approaches overlap in time and are tightly related (see Figure 1 and Figure 2 below)

Figure 1: **Research process with CSO organisers**

The research with the CSOs for WP2 is two-fold. It consists of 1) the ethnographic fieldwork in 3 CSOs to understand the context in which the CSO works, the activities they organise and the audience they reach, and 2) the FGDs with CSO representatives and staff members to understand their views on gender empowerment and inclusion.

Step 1: Selection and recruitment of CSOs

In each fieldwork country, we aim to select three CSOs that participate in the fieldwork. The first CSO to be selected is the CSO included in the consortium. The CSOs should envision empowerment and inclusion of their members with a focus on migrant women and cover different fields of support and activities. They should also ideally have different sizes and structures. Depending on the national context, they might not be in the same locality. However, due to the longer duration of the ethnographic fieldwork CSOs will most likely be situated in the same locality as the main partners.

To enter the field, research partners will organize a designated introductory meeting with the selected CSOs to explain in more details the logic of the ethnographic research and the level of engagement and time resources that are expected from them. A step-by-step description of what ethnographic research and participant observation implies in practice should be provided. Conditions of anonymity and privacy, as well as withdrawing consent at any given moment should be explicitly discussed. The ethics protocols from WP1 should be strictly followed.

We aim to explicitly state our respectful approach. An initial negotiation and agreement of which activities are appropriate for participant observation should take place in the beginning and left open for negotiation at any stage of the research.

Step 2 FGD with CSOs organisers/staff members: The Focus Group Discussions with CSO staff should take place at the beginning of the research period and include staff members at different levels of the organisation (e.g., director and social worker, volunteers etc.). A total of 3 FGDs planned - one in each CSO.

Step 3: Ethnographic observations (see section 2.2.): The ethnographic observation consists of at least 20 contact moments with each CSO which can be spread throughout the research period, depending on the scheduled activities, projects and trajectories. It can overlap with the organisations FGDs in time.

Step 4: An optional fourth FGD can be planned, which could be organised with representatives of each CSO part of our fieldwork and other CSOs working on similar topics in the same local CSO landscape. This FGD can be scheduled at the end of the research period. It can also overlap with a second CSO Advisory board and take the format of a more structured debate. We could then ask this CSO board to be recorded and used for analytical purposes. This is at the discretion of each research partner.

Figure 2: Research process with CSO participants

Research with CSO participants will be organised in several stages and contains of two main research approaches: 1) **photo voicing interviews** and 2) **focus group discussions**

Step 1: Recruiting participants for the interviews and organising introductory sessions and a photovoice workshop.

Step 2: Individual interviews with 10 participants per CSO: The interviews with each participant are conducted at three moments in time and follow the structure described in 2.4.

Step 3: FGD with CSO participants: One FGD per CSO with participants from their target groups, i.e. a total of 3 FGDs with participants. They should take place after the initial interviews are conducted and build on the knowledge and analysis of the first and second photovoice interviews. The participants in the FGDs do not have to be the same as the participants in the individual interviews, but they can overlap.

Step 4: In the process of conducting the photo-voice interviews, CSO participants will be invited to participate in an art exhibition and a photo-essay book (led by FMV). The final interaction with the participants is a presentation of the art exhibition and photo-essay book.

ETHNOGRAPHIC OBSERVATIONS

The explorative ethnographic fieldwork will provide data for both WP2 and WP3. It involves observation of organisational cultures, implementation of policies and ongoing practices (such as organised activities, relations and dynamics between CSO staff and target groups and within the CSO teams). It also gives researchers access and opportunity to discuss with the CSO organisers concrete instances or occurrences and collect additional conceptualizations and ways of thinking and working with the concepts of (gender) empowerment and inclusion in practice and in concrete situations. It also gives context to activities and approaches. The exploration of activities, events, spaces and services provided to women from the target groups will contribute to WP3. At the same time, the meticulous mapping of the CSO through ethnographic fieldwork will provide the context and the possible tensions and spaces of negotiation for CSO organisers and members in how they define gender empowerment. In conducting the ethnographic fieldwork, we will follow an organisational ethnographic approach.

The ethnographic fieldwork in the CSOs is inspired by the method of **organisational ethnography**. It is considered a distinct approach which is concerned with social relations that are related to goal-directed activities. It is considered that rules, strategies and meanings within a structured work situation are different from those that affect other areas of social life (Bryman & Bell, 2007). Moreover, Cunliffe (2010) argues that good organisational ethnographies can reveal and explore the intricacies, challenges, tensions, and choices of life in organisations. Immersion through participant observation allows the researcher to explore the complexities of everyday organisational life and to unpack the taken-for-granted dynamics and activities that insiders might not be able to formulate in interviews and narrative formats. Organisational ethnography has the potential of making explicit meaning-making processes that might otherwise remain hidden or overlooked. (Ybema & Kamsteed, 2009). Finally, it encourages context-sensitive and actor-centred analysis which combines subjective experiences and individual agency with broader social settings and institutional dynamics in which these are embedded.

Given the time constraints of the project, we propose to follow a script for a rapid ethnography in organisations. Rapid ethnographies, in particular, have become increasingly popular since the 2010s. Focused, quick, rapid, or short-term ethnography are terms used in the literature to describe ethnographic research that does not span over the classical one-year immersion in the field. (Kumpunen & Padros 2022). A rapid ethnography is conducted over a short intensive period of time, captures contextual social and cultural information, focuses on experiences and practices. Data is collected from multiple sources and is triangulated during the analysis. Findings are fed back while the research is ongoing and research is adjusted to complement the ongoing analysis. The research can use more than one field researcher to save time and provide multiple perspectives, to speed-up the analysis and cross-check data (Vindrola-Padros & Vindrola-Padros, 2018).

Participant observation: main steps and techniques

Within the context of organisational ethnography, we aim to adopt participant observation as the main ethnographic technique to be used in this stage of the research. Participant observation is a technique of immersion and participation of the researcher. Research aims to understand the dynamics, behaviours, interactions, practices and activities, as well as the ways the participants make sense and conceptualise them. It provides a better understanding of the social context and of the non-verbal aspects that do not always get narrated. It involves observation, structured conversations (or semi-structured interviews), and participation in activities. By participating, the researchers have the opportunity to better understand the activities and the relationships. Gaining a glimpse into the 'insider's perspective fosters an adjustment of the positionality of the researcher as observed from outside.

For each CSO, we aim to observe 20 contact moments as participant observers taking structured fieldnotes. These contact moments should include both the regular activities of the CSO and extraordinary one-off events or activities to cover the full spectrum

Preparation for fieldwork: Context and Background research

- Literature review on available secondary sources on gender empowerment in each country, mapping of the key CSOs in the field in each respective country, and on the policy context related to gender empowerment (completed as part of task 2.1 and 2.2.).
- Collect information and draft CSO profiles in advance through websites, initial information from the partnering CSO and the CSO board. The aim is to identify the main objectives and the social problem they address, the main activities, size of the organisation and type and level of engagement, target groups, participation in projects and main activities, members, levels of engagement, and main organisational documents.

Negotiating access to the field and working methods

The introduction of the project and the negotiation of the time and efforts to be spent by the CSOs should have been discussed at the recruitment meeting as well as asking for permission, using an informed consent (see D1.1.). In the introductory session the main points should be repeated, emphasising the role of the researcher and the main research activities that will be conducted. If more than one researcher

will conduct the research, this should be stated from the beginning and all involved should be presented. Feedback is encouraged on the role and involvement of the researcher throughout the fieldwork process.

Points to consider:

- **Time and schedule:** time spent by co-workers to explain how the organisation functions and how the activities are organised
- **Position of the researcher:** concrete time and type of involvement, role and possible contribution
- **Ethical issues, informed consent, anonymity, privacy:** All ethical protocols and informed consent forms should be reviewed in detail with the CSO representative before the start of the ethnographic fieldwork. Where needed, forms should be adjusted and translated into relevant languages. Rules should be agreed upon in advance and conformed to.

When stating the aim of the project, the researchers should remain at a more general level, in order not to pre-define the concepts or to limit the topics that might appear during the research.

The issue of trust should be addressed in the beginning and in the process of conducting the fieldwork, as well as during the FGDs with CSO organisers. Information that CSO organisers might regard as internal, or potentially harming for the CSO, should not be further disclosed in the analysis and reporting. A mechanism for indicating and for feedback should be agreed upon in the beginning.

Conducting participant observation, main steps and techniques

The main goal is to **become familiar with the field**. This involves getting to know the organisation of the space, the different people and their positions, the activities that are organised and the services provided, the time schedules. Discuss one-off events immediately, and plan which ones to attend. Fieldwork involves observation and participation of events and activities, and everyday interactions and ways of functioning of the organization. Fieldwork diary is not a must, observations should be written up in a report format, following the points below. (See Observation guidelines in the Annex 1)

While we do not aim to burden the CSO employees who will be our main interlocutors, we would also like to engage in discussions with them on their vision of gender empowerment and inclusion, and the potential negotiations and tensions they might identify at different levels between their own motivations and conceptualizations and the way funding and bureaucratic models and procedures define their CSOs mission and activities.

Informal discussions and conversations with CSO organisers and running commentary should accompany the observations. They should be focused on interpretations of what is going on and how the CSO organisers interpret the activities, practices and main goals of the organisation in the context of gender empowerment. Being there and having short discussions around a particular event, activity, or concrete issues or problems that the target groups might face, gives an opportunity to understand in more details the ideas about gender empowerment that CSO organisers have.

FOCUS GROUP DISCUSSIONS WITH CSO STAFF AND PARTICIPANTS

FGD will be conducted both with CSO staff members and with CSO participants from their target groups. There will be three FGDs with CSO staff members (one per CSO) and three FGDs with participants (one per CSO). Thus, a total of 6 FGDs per country should be conducted during the research phase.

FGD with CSO staff members

At the start of each fieldwork, one FGD is planned with CSO organisers per CSO, including staff members at all levels of this organisation. The aim of the FGDs is two-fold. First, to assess the conceptualisation of gender empowerment and inclusion. Second, to highlight the CSO practices that stimulate gender empowerment and inclusion (this will feed data for WP3 as well). This is necessary to further gain more information on the conditions and structures in which gender empowerment practices and other CSO practices are implemented, needed to provide input for the digital tool. A fourth optional FGD that includes representatives of each CSO and other CSOs can be scheduled at the end of the research period. It can also overlap with a second Advisory board and take the format of a more structured debate, be recorded and used for analytical purposes. This is at the discretion of each research partner. This will take place towards the end of the intensive research phase with representatives of the researched CSOs, and also help to incorporate knowledge gathered during the ethnographic fieldwork and conversations.

A topic guide for the FGD with CSO staff members can be found in Annex 2. At the start of each FGD, please, circulate the Drop-off form to collect anonymous demographic information (see Annex 5)

FGD with CSO participants

The FGD discussions with CSO participants are planned for the second half of the research period, after initial photo voicing interviews have been conducted. The participants in each FGD can be among those who were already interviewed, but can also be other people from the target groups. Language should be considered when selecting the participants for each FGD. Multi-language discussions might be difficult to moderate, but these options should be considered, if the target groups of a given CSO have a diverse composition and the researchers find it necessary to include representatives of different linguistic groups.

The topic guide for each FGD can be updated after initial interviews have been conducted, to reflect the main concerns and issues. An initial topic guide; for the FGDs with CSO participants is provided in Annex 3. At the start of each FGD, please, circulate the Drop-off form to collect anonymous demographic information (see Annex 6)

PHOTO-VOICE TRAJECTORIES

What is Photo-Voicing?

Photo-Voicing is a methodological technique that was first developed by Wang and Burris in 1998, for research on public health where it is still applied for the most part. However, the technique is “*highly flexible and can be adapted to specific participatory goals, different groups and communities*”. The core of the photovoice methodology is that the studied group receives photography training and is instructed to take pictures of anything (themselves, others, places, or things) they deem important in regard to a

specific subject. Afterwards, the photos are shared and discussed individually or in a group in the format of a focus group discussion (Wang & Burris, 1997; Duffy, 2011). Photo-voicing has been used as a research method to reach more vulnerable groups, to discuss difficult to conceptualise questions, and to express ideas beyond language. Photovoice can be used as a technique in itself, primarily focused on the pictures, or as an auxiliary technique to assist with interviews on complicated topics.

In the context of ReIncluGen, photovoice is a research method to understand concepts of gender empowerment in an emic, inductive and collaborative way. Asking women to take pictures and using them as an entry point allows the interview to be led by the ideas and concepts of the women, rather than to have preconceived questions and indicators of gender empowerment imposed from outside by the researcher. In a classic interview the questions, the formulations, the order of how they are asked, can pre-define the way interlocutors formulate their answers. By using photo-voicing, we want to avoid this and leave the conceptualizations of gender empowerment stem from the women and their views. In this way, it is the woman who leads, decides and selects the topics, the ways they are approached, and the emphases. Thus, it enables the researchers to understand more deeply why the photos were taken as they were, what the people tried to express, what and why this is of importance to them and how they are viewed in the group.

Photovoice is an especially promising technique when working with participants, who are stigmatised, vulnerable, or who find it difficult to articulate ideas just in a narrative or interview format (Wang & Burris, 1997). Furthermore, through photovoice it is possible to receive insights that the research normally would not have access to or participants could focus on aspects the researcher would not have thought of as relevant (Wang & Burris; Cooper & Yarbrough, 2010). Finally, this is a particularly good technique for discussing topics that might be controversial or where the researcher and the interlocutor might have diverging takes on the very definitions of what is being discussed.

In conclusion, by directly including the participants in several steps of the research process, the research itself is highly participatory and co-creative (Liebenberg, 2018). As such, it could be empowering, shifting the control over the research process and the main categories and definitions from the researcher to the interlocutor (Budig et al., 1998). The women take the lead in defining and crafting meanings. The process of selecting pictures and attributing meanings to them is shifting the creative process to the person, rather than imposed from outside. It allows for truly inductive and collaborative research.

Finally, the produced picture “*can be a source of pride and ownership*”, especially in the context of making them public (Wang & Burris, 1997).

As photo-voicing is an explorative, inductive method, please, pay close attention to keeping the wording as neutral and as open as possible throughout all stages. We are all biased and with pre-defined concepts of what gender empowerment means, what is the role and position of women in societies, etc. While we cannot completely step out of our positionality as researchers, we need to pay attention to our wording, to our silences and to allowing our co-researchers to lead the process and define the directions, topics and the tone of the interviews.

Photo-elicited interviews

We invite 10 participants per CSO and conduct three consecutive interviews with each participant.

Before starting these interviews, the researchers could opt to organise a **photography workshop**. The aim of the workshop is to provide women with skills and to create a group environment where they can learn new techniques and practice taking photos. The workshop can be organised at a later stage, at the discretion of the research team, to assist women who have already participated in the interviews, to take additional pictures for the art exhibition. The aim is not only to inform the participants about the technical aspects of taking pictures, but “*also to discuss the role of photography as a representational tool. [...] so that participants consciously make decisions about who, what and how to represent themselves and community life in their photographs.*” (Boonzaier & Kessi, 2018).

The researcher should decide whether to approach CSO participants for a group introductory session, or discuss it individually with each participant. The introduction should include: Ethics and Informed consent forms (see D1.1). Introduce the photo voicing procedure. Present the art exhibition and photo/essay book

- **First interview:** discuss the objectives, start from a biographical narrative approach including the participants’ life trajectory. This interview is needed to discuss ‘gender empowerment’ in laymen terms and discuss the potential photos the women could take. At the end of the interview the participant is asked to take or bring photos (3-5 per person) to the next meeting. Prompts of what the pictures should represent are given to the participant at this point.
- **Second interview:** the second interview is structured around the photographs: why they took them, what do they represent. The interviewer should ask questions to make links between the first interview and the photos. Between the second and the third interview, the participant could take more pictures, inspired by the discussion or to take alternative pictures that they want to share publicly, if the ones taken before are considered private.
- **Third interview:** In this step, the participant chooses a picture to be included in the essay book and art exhibition. If they do not want to include any of the pictures taken by them¹, the interviewer should discuss what kind of pictures they want to share. This interview is centred around questions of representation, empowerment through images and participating in a public event. Explain that this is voluntary and not everyone who participated in the interview has to contribute with a picture, unless they choose to do so.

The interview topic guides are as follows:

- Introduction (see D1.1.): State the aims and objectives of the project and the main question, ask to fill in an informed consent and explain the ethics guidelines. (to be used before Interview 1)
- Annex 4A, Interview 1 - trajectory and photo prompts
- Annex 4B, Interview 2 - photo voicing questions
- Annex 4C, Interview 3 - selecting the photos for art exhibition and follow-up questions

¹ Another way to go is for the ethnographers and professional photographers ideally from the CSO's to go to the selected person's home. Documentary photographs are taken of the process of 'selection' of objects. End up taking one or several portraits and photographs of objects in a co-creative way.

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ANNEX 1. GUIDELINE OBSERVATIONS

Topic guideline for ethnographic fieldwork:

A) Structure, Policies and Practices of the CSOs

- Note and describe the structure of the organisation, its members, the hierarchies
- Observe relations and dynamics between the team. How are the different tasks distributed, how many team members are working on different tasks. How many external and how many permanent staff members, and how is work distributed between them. (For example – language courses, counselling, project management and funding applications, organisation of social spaces, management and HR, etc)
- Observe workload, task distribution (hint – burnt out and working over hours is a recognized problem in some CSOs working in the field, support staff)
- Relations between CSOs employees and beneficiaries / target group women?
- Power dynamics and top-down/bottom-up approaches. How are decisions taken?
- Languages spoken – is there a shared language between women and CSO organisers who are not working directly with them? Is there a shared language between the different groups of women that come to the activities?
- Special events and activities that are not part of regular activities of the CSOs – follow the calendar and visit as many as possible in the research period. Not how are they organised, what is their focus, who participates, especially if more people come than the regular beneficiaries of the CSO
- Particular focus on socialising events and provision of spaces for socialisation and community building. Describe if there are any and how are they organised, whether they are formal, as part of a project or informally providing the spaces of the organisation.
- Extra services provided that go beyond the scope of the core activities of the CSO

B) CSOs proposals for change (to provide material for WP3)

- What's the 'problem' (for example, of 'problem gamblers', 'drug use/abuse', 'gender inequality', 'domestic violence', 'global warming', 'sexual harassment', etc.) represented to be in a specific policy or policy proposal? (Policy or activity)
- What presuppositions or assumptions underpin this representation of the 'problem'?
- How has this representation of the 'problem' come about?
- What is left unproblematic in this problem representation? Where are the silences? Can the 'problem' be thought about differently? (For example, by different actors, at different levels, etc.)
- What effects are produced by this representation of the 'problem'?
- How/where has this representation of the problem been produced, disseminated, and defended? How could it be questioned, disrupted, and replaced?

ANNEX 2. TOPIC GUIDE FOCUS GROUP DISCUSSIONS WITH CSO STAFF

MEMBERS

The aim of the FGDs is two-fold. First, to assess the conceptualisation of gender empowerment and inclusion. Second, to highlight the CSO practices that stimulate gender empowerment and inclusion. The different parts of the discussion can be moved around, depending on how the discussion unfolds.

Introduction

- **Welcome** the participants and thank them for their time and willingness to share their views and experiences. Ask them to fill the Drop-off form (Annex 5) and to hand it in at the end
- **Introduce yourself and the purpose of the study:** We are conducting this focus group as part of a research project on gender empowerment in civil society organizations. We want to understand how you perceive and experience gender empowerment and inclusion in your work, what are the challenges and opportunities, and what are your suggestions for improvement.
- **Explain the ground rules:** This is a confidential and voluntary discussion. There are no right or wrong answers, only different opinions and perspectives. We encourage you to respect each other's views and listen attentively. We will record the discussion for analysis purposes, but we will not use your names or identify you in any way. You can withdraw from the discussion at any time if you feel uncomfortable.
- **Ask for consent:** Consent forms are distributed and signed. Do you have any questions before we start? Are you comfortable with these rules and willing to participate? If the ethics form from D1.1. have not been yet signed by the participants, this should be done before the discussion begins.

Warm-up

- Ask each participant to introduce themselves by saying their name, role, and how long they have been working in their organisation.

Main discussion - Part 1 Profile of the organization

1. What is the main goal of your organization?
2. Which are the main target groups?
3. What issues are being addressed in your organisation?
4. What issues or problems do you think are left out? Why do you think this happens?
5. What are your main needs as an organization?

6. What are the main needs of the target groups that you work with? In terms of gender empowerment, and in terms of inclusion?

Main discussion - part 2: Conceptualizations of gender empowerment

7. What does gender empowerment mean to you in your work context? How would you define whether others are empowered or disempowered?
8. How about inclusion? What is your definition of inclusion?
9. Can you give some examples of situations or practices that promote or hinder gender empowerment in the context of your organisation?
10. Does your definition of gender empowerment and the one of your organisation overlap?
11. Do you think there are discrepancies between your vision of gender empowerment and inclusion and the way the people who come to your organisation envision it? Does this create tensions? How do you solve them?

Main discussion - part 3: Good practices. SWOT

12. What is a good practice in your organization? Why?

Define good practices first, listing the following criteria

- Have a clear description of the objectives and purposes
- Have a clear description of the actions/activities involved
- Be at least one year old
- Meet clearly identified needs?
- Engage stakeholders and target groups?
- Continue after the initial phase? i.e. be sustainable
- Be funded (attract structural funding, support from new sponsors or generate its own resources)
- Show potential for replication in different contexts and towards different target groups?

13. What is a practice or approach that makes your organization special or different than the others working in the same field?
14. What are the main challenges or barriers that prevent you or others from achieving gender empowerment and inclusion? How do you cope with or overcome them?
15. What are the main opportunities or enablers that support achieving gender empowerment through our organisation? How do you leverage or create them?

16. What are your suggestions or recommendations for improving the process of achieving gender empowerment through your organisation? What actions can you take individually or collectively? What actions can your organisation take at different levels (e.g., policies, culture, leadership, etc.)?

17. **SWOT** (strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats).

Explain what is a *swot* and bring a cardboard and more post-it notes. If some of the questions had come up already in the discussion, summarize them and sort them in the chart

You will ask them to think about the strengths and weaknesses of their organisation in order to tackle the problems around gender empowerment and inclusion. You will explain the difference between external threats and opportunities (and you can put examples they have already expressed) which are conditioned by the context, and the internal strengths and weaknesses related to their own organisation.

Closing

- Summarize the main points of the discussion and ask for confirmation or clarification if needed.
- Thank the participants again for their participation and valuable insights.
- Ask for feedback on the discussion process and any final comments or questions.
- Explain the next steps of the study, especially in view of the ethnographic fieldwork, and how the results will be used and shared.

ANNEX 3. TOPIC GUIDE FOCUS GROUP DISCUSSION WITH CSO PARTICIPANTS

Introduction

- Welcome the participants and thank them for their time and willingness to share their views and experiences. Ask them to fill the Drop-off form (Annex 6) without inserting their name and to hand it in at the end.
- Introduce yourself and the purpose of the study: We are conducting this focus group as part of a research project on gender empowerment in civil society organisations. We want to understand how you perceive and experience gender empowerment in your work, what are the challenges and opportunities, and what are your suggestions for improvement. At this point most of the participants already know you and the project so this can be done in an informal way.
- Explain the ground rules: This is a confidential and voluntary discussion. There are no right or wrong answers, only different opinions and perspectives. We encourage you to respect each other's views and listen attentively. We will record the discussion for analysis purposes, but we will not use your names or identify you in any way. You can withdraw from the discussion at any time if you feel uncomfortable.
- Ask for consent: Do you have any questions before we start? Are you comfortable with these rules and willing to participate? If the ethics form from D1.1. have not been yet signed by the participants, this should be done before the discussion begins.

Definitions and Concepts

1. Ask each participant to introduce themselves by saying their name, and other information they find important and comfortable to share, like country of origin, what they do, and how long they have been living in this country.
2. Explain that the project works with the word 'gender empowerment' (in English), which is a difficult word to translate and it might mean different things for different people.

Then ask each participant to come up with one word that come to mind when they think of 'gender empowerment' (or 'women empowerment', if appropriate)

3. Ask each participant to give an example with a situation or a quality that they think of when they think of gender empowerment
4. Explain that the following questions will be connected to gender empowerment and inclusion that way each participant understands these concepts and you can come back to these concepts at the end.

Write down the main concepts that came up in the discussion and return to them as an addition to 'gender empowerment' in each of the questions bellow, if needed.

Main discussion

1. What does 'gender empowerment' mean to you in your life context? How do you know when you or others are empowered or disempowered?
2. How do you experience 'gender empowerment' or disempowerment in this country? Can you give some examples of situations or practices that promote or hinder gender empowerment?
3. How does 'gender empowerment' affect your well-being, inclusion, participation, and rights?
4. What would you need to feel good as a woman? What are the main barriers, what are the main support mechanisms?
5. What would you need for your daughter to feel good as a woman? What, do you think, might stop her or help her in this?
6. Who can support you in feeling good as a woman (to feel empowered and included)?

Closing

- Summarize the main points of the discussion and ask for confirmation or clarification if needed.
- Thank the participants again for their participation and valuable insights.
- Explain the next steps of the study and how the results will be used and shared.
- Ask for feedback on the discussion process and any final comments or questions

ANNEX 4. TOPIC GUIDE INTERVIEW PHOTO-VOICING

All interviews start with an introduction and discussion and signing of the interviews consent forms

- Quick introduction of the researcher (and translator).
- Repeat the main idea of the project and the aim of the interviews and ethics guidelines
- Agree explicitly about recording the interview (part of the consent form)

Annex 4A: Interview 1

I. Discussing life trajectories and gender

1. Could you tell us a bit more about your life trajectory? How was it growing up and living in your country of origin? What has changed the most since you live here? (How did your life look like so far)

Prompts: relationships, education, labour market participation, migration, etc.

2. When discussing your life trajectory, which aspects are you most proud of/ are most important to you?

Prompts: we want to know about personal achievements, in what sphere they are, and to what extent they are considered as important and valuable.

3. Which aspects in your life did you consider difficult? What helped you to go through these phases?
4. What would you like the future to look like for you?
5. During your life, could you tell us more on how gender (your role as a woman) played a role in your own life trajectory?
 - a. Do you think this is similar for other women? why (not)?
 - b. Do you think it would have been different if you lived elsewhere? why (not)?
6. Do you feel you are part of *Austrian/Belgian/Italian/Polish/Spanish* society? Why (not)?

Prompts: Ask about inclusion or participation socially, culturally, politically?

II. Discussing CSO practices

7. Could you tell us how you found this CSO? What kind of services and support do they provide for you?
8. How do you think women like you are strengthened by / What has (positively) changed in your life since you are taking part in the activities of [name CSO]?
9. Do you feel that there are any barriers for you (and what kind) in the CSO?
10. What do you miss or what could be done better?
11. Do you think the practices of this CSO are welcoming to everybody and inclusive ?

III. Discussion the concept 'gender empowerment' and preparing for the photo prompts

12. Empowerment is a difficult term to define. How would you translate it in your language? What would it mean to you?

IV. Describe the Photo task and give prompts

The researcher explains the approach of discussing ideas through photos and providing the prompts for the pictures that they can take and bring to the second interview. The concepts *empowerment*, *inclusion*, *equality* should be taken up from question 12 and used as a starting point.

The aim is to bring 3 to 5 photos of people, situations, object. They can be new photos, taken for the occasion, old photos taken by them, from a photo album etc, or photos of other people. The participant is free to decide how many they will bring.

Prompts are given as an idea of what the photos should be

- A photo that represents yourself
- A photo of a person or a situation that you aspire to
- A picture of yourself or of a situation in which you like yourself
- A photo where you feel empowered (it could be of yourself, a situation, an object, someone else)
- A photo of what it means to be a woman (like yourself or like 'other' women)?
- A photo that reminds you of any relevant moment of your live when you managed to overcome a difficulty/

Annex 4B: Interview 2

The photo-voicing interview should be centred at the participant and the researcher should follow her lead. The photos are used as a starting point to discuss the topics of empowerment, inclusion, and equality. The focus is on how they see themselves, how they position themselves vis-à-vis others, what barriers or enabling mechanisms they think of when they think of empowerment. A link with the work of the CSOs should be looked for, when follow up questions are asked.

Selection of photos

1. Which photo do you want to start with?
2. Which prompt inspired you to take this photo?
3. Why did you choose this photo?

Discussion of photos

1. What do you see here?
2. How does it relate to being a woman?
3. Why did you take this picture?
4. What quality does it portray/exhibit?
5. Does this picture represent empowerment (or whatever word you agreed on in the previous interview) in some form? And why?
6. Do you feel you already have this (quality, condition, trait, ...)?
7. How do you think you can achieve it?

Connect with the themes from the first interview, reflect on their life trajectories, how they define gender empowerment and inclusion.

Additional Themes to ask during the discussion of the pictures, if they do not come up naturally. They can be inserted in-between the above questions to probe further into the opinion or conceptualizations of the women.

- The role of women, Translocality/Comparison between different communities and societies.
- Challenges/Support: What is stopping you from achieving the things you want? What supports you? What other needs do you have?
- Agency/Autonomy/Independence/Freedom/Strength/Inclusion/Equality/Other: If any of these concepts come up in the discussion of empowerment, ask What does it mean to you? Give me an example of a situation where you felt this?

Annex 4C: Interview 3

Revisit interview 2 themes

This part of the interview is devoted to coming back to the themes from Interview TWO and revisiting some of the ideas. If new pictures are brought, this can be further discussed. Themes that might have remained unfinished in the previous interview can be raised again. It should start with a question of whether the woman thought about these issues, whether she thought of something else she might want to share or another picture that she took in the meantime

- How did the discussion make you feel afterwards?
- Did something new come to mind in the meantime? Would you like to show new pictures?
- Did you like expressing yourself through images?
- Would you want to share images of yourself or pictures that you took/authored with others? Do you think this might help other people understand your situation and your needs better?

Discuss the photo/essay book and the art exhibition

Explain in more details the idea of the photo book and the art exhibition. Discuss what pictures the participant might want to share. This is not the first time they should hear about this. You can go together through the pictures that she selected. This interview aims to gain insights on their ideas of public representation, of how they want to share their ideas, or prefer not to participate, or whether they want to show their faces or prefer to remain anonymous. Accompanying the picture with short narratives/essays should also be discussed at this stage. This will make the process of selecting and creating the final products more collaborative.

Wrap up

More details on the selection process and the finalisation of the photo book and the art exhibition should be presented at the end of the interview – details about this will be further developed.

ANNEX 5. DROP-OFF FORM FOR CSO STAFF

Drop off for CSO staff in focus group discussions

Organisation:	
Function title:	
Main tasks:	
Years working at the organisation:	
Gender:	<input type="checkbox"/> male <input type="checkbox"/> female <input type="checkbox"/> other.....
Age (years):	
Neighbourhood (postal code)	
Country of birth:	
Country of birth mother:	
Country of birth father:	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Islam

Religious affiliation:	• Christianity
	• Judaism
	• Buddhism
	• Hinduism
	• Atheist
	• Other
Employment status:	• Employed
	• Unemployed
	• Not eligible
	• Other
Educational level:	• Higher education
	• Secondary education
	• Primary education
	• Non formal education
Languages spoken:	

ANNEX 6. DROP-OFF FORM FOR CSO PARTICIPANTS

Drop off for CSO participants (interviews + FGD)

Organisation where FGD takes place	
Gender:	<input type="checkbox"/> male <input type="checkbox"/> female <input type="checkbox"/> other
Partner:	<input type="checkbox"/> yes <input type="checkbox"/> no
Age (years):	
Children (if yes: how many + ages):	
Time of residence in the country (in years):	
Neighbourhood (postal code):	
Country of birth:	
Country of birth mother:	
Country of birth father:	
Country of residence before the current country:	

Religious affiliation:	• Islam
	• Christianity
	• Judaism
	• Buddhism
	• Hinduism
	• Atheist
	• Other
Employment status:	• Employed
	• Unemployed
	• Not eligible
	• Other
Educational level:	• Higher education
	• Secondary education
	• Primary education
	• Non formal education
Current profession:	
Profession in country of origin:	
Alphabetization:	0 yes 0 no
Languages spoken	